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Introduction.

Synchrotron radiation sources are pulsed X-ray sources with typical pulse lengths of 100 ps and inter-pulse distance of some nanoseconds up to about 200 ns. This pulsed source can be accounted as continuous for standard applications with acquisition times of more than 0.01 s and relatively slow change of actuators or other devices, with “slow” meaning a speed of one X-ray beam diameter per 0.01 seconds. Should an experiment require much higher speeds, e.g. for pump-probe measurements, the granularity of the X-ray beam has to be considered or is even required to collect meaningful data. For this a synchronization of beamline devices, such as detectors, the accelerator clock and external fields is realized by means of fast electronics.

In the future, with detectors operating at acquisition rates of more than 100 kHz and with voice coil and piezo stages reaching speeds of 1m/s, synchronization will be required even for non-pump-probe measurements. By offering a human- and machine-readable protocol, which describes the synchronization tasks for an experiment, the installation of an experiments becomes straight forward at the different synchrotron radiation sources. The protocol should be useful for users and for the staff of these X-ray sources.

This protocol, as presented here, is the result of the Task 5.3 “Synchronization of beamline components” of the LEAP-INNOV project. It needs still rigorous testing and gets therefore version number 0.9

General remarks to the synchronization protocol

The experimentalist comes to the facility with a certain equipment/hardware to run the experiment. The synchronization of this equipment with the beamline and the accelerator is key for the success of the experiment. He/she must describe the synchronization that this equipment needs by submitting a form. The output of this form is a JSON data file. This data file is processed to 1) check that it fits the beamline capabilities 2) configure the beamline synchronization equipment for that experiment. Each required signal will be defined independently. The format of the protocol is strictly defined and contains following notations:

- Key words are in the following printed with bold characters.
- The setup with synchronized hardware devices is controlled via **Signals**.
- Each **Signal** is described by mandatory **Descriptors**.
- Each **Signal** must have a **Descriptor** 'Name'. The **Descriptors** 'Name' of all **Signals** must not be pairwise identical. The names of **Descriptors** are marked by single quotation marks.
- Each **Descriptor** has at least one **Value** with given **Type** and, if applicable, given **Unit**.
- Numbers are of **Type Integer** or **Float**. The third valid **Type** is **Text**, a case sensitive string.
- A **Descriptor** can contain other **Descriptors**.
- The value of **Values** can be restricted to certain **KeyWords**. **KeyWords** are marked by double quotation marks.

The symbol # is used to separate the protocol content

The format of the synchronization protocol

The format for **Signal** is as follows. Multiple **Signals** with different **Descriptors** 'Name' can be combined for one experiment. The They JSON scheme is listed at the end of this document.

Signal:

```
Name: Text
Description: Text
Direction: Input | Output
FormFactor: BNC | SMA | LEMO_00 | FO
Type: Trigger | Gate | Analog
Reference: None | RF_signal | External_Clk | Internal_Clk | Event | Signal | Analog
Inhibit: None | Signal
```

```
DigitalParameters: #Required fields if 'Trigger' or 'Gate' are selected as Type
Signaling: TTL | LVTTTL | CMOS | 500hm | OpenCollector | OpenEmitter | Voltage
Polarity: ActiveHigh | ActiveLow # For trigger: Active High = rising edge
ActiveTime: Integer [ps]
DeadTime: Integer [ps]
RiseTime: Integer [ps]
FallTime: Integer [ps]
MaxJitter: Integer [ps]
HighVoltage: Float [V] #Required field if 'Voltage' is selected as Signaling
LowVoltage: Float [V] #Required field if 'Voltage' is selected as Signaling
```

```
AnalogParameters: #Required fields if 'Analog' is selected as Type
MaxVoltage: Float [V]
BitDepth: Integer
```

```
ReferenceParameters:
REventNumber: Integer #Required field if 'Event' is selected as Reference
RSignalName: Text #Required field if 'Signal' is selected as Reference
RAnalogMin: Float #Required field if 'Analog' is selected as Reference
RAnalogMax: Float #Required field if 'Analog' is selected as Reference
```

```
InhibitParameters:
ISignalName: Text #Required field if 'Signal' is selected as Reference
IPolarity: ActiveHigh | ActiveLow #Required field if 'Signal' is select. as Reference
```

```
ModifierParameters:
Divider: Integer #Required field if 'Trigger' or 'Gate' are selected as Type
Holdoff: Integer [ps] #Required field if 'Trigger' or 'Gate' is selected as Type
Delay: Integer [ps] #Required field if 'Trigger' or 'Gate' is selected as Type
ADivider: Float #Required field if 'Analog' is selected as Type
```


Detailed description of the mandatory descriptors of signal

‘Name’	of Type Text . All ‘Names’ of all Signals in an experiment must be pairwise different.								
‘Description’	of Type Text .								
‘Direction’	of Type case sensitive string. Can only be one of the following KeyWords : “Input” or “Output”. The KeyWords mean the following: <table border="0" style="margin-left: 40px;"> <tr> <td style="padding-right: 20px;">“Input”</td> <td>This Signal does not create and output (e.g. detector)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>“Output”</td> <td>This Signal creates an output signal</td> </tr> </table>	“Input”	This Signal does not create and output (e.g. detector)	“Output”	This Signal creates an output signal				
“Input”	This Signal does not create and output (e.g. detector)								
“Output”	This Signal creates an output signal								
‘Formfactor’	of Type case sensitive string. Can only be one of the following KeyWords : “BNC” or “SMA” or “LEMO_00” or “FO”. The KeyWords mean the following: <table border="0" style="margin-left: 40px;"> <tr> <td style="padding-right: 20px;">“BNC”</td> <td>Plug is BNC</td> </tr> <tr> <td>“SMA”</td> <td>Plug is SMA</td> </tr> <tr> <td>“LEMO_00”</td> <td>Plug is Lemo 00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>“FO”</td> <td>Fiber Optics</td> </tr> </table>	“BNC”	Plug is BNC	“SMA”	Plug is SMA	“LEMO_00”	Plug is Lemo 00	“FO”	Fiber Optics
“BNC”	Plug is BNC								
“SMA”	Plug is SMA								
“LEMO_00”	Plug is Lemo 00								
“FO”	Fiber Optics								
‘Type’	of Type case sensitive string. Can only be one of the following KeyWords : “Trigger”, “Gate”, “Analog”. The KeyWords mean the following: <table border="0" style="margin-left: 40px;"> <tr> <td style="padding-right: 20px;">“Trigger”</td> <td>raising or falling edges as input or outputs</td> </tr> <tr> <td>“Gate”</td> <td>switches between low and high state</td> </tr> <tr> <td>“Analog”</td> <td>creates or receives analog values (e.g. from ADC, encoder etc)</td> </tr> </table>	“Trigger”	raising or falling edges as input or outputs	“Gate”	switches between low and high state	“Analog”	creates or receives analog values (e.g. from ADC, encoder etc)		
“Trigger”	raising or falling edges as input or outputs								
“Gate”	switches between low and high state								
“Analog”	creates or receives analog values (e.g. from ADC, encoder etc)								
‘Reference’	of Type case sensitive string. Can only be one of the following KeyWords : “None”, “RF_Signal”, “External_Clock”, “Internal_Clock”, “Event”, “Signal” or “Analog”. The ‘Reference’ determines, how the input/output of ‘Signal’ is handled. ‘Reference’ contains Descriptors (see below). The KeyWords mean the following: <table border="0" style="margin-left: 40px;"> <tr> <td style="padding-right: 20px;">“None”</td> <td>The signal does not follow a reference (e.g. a detector would be of ‘Direction’ “Input” and doesn’t require a ‘Reference’).</td> </tr> <tr> <td>“RF_Signal”</td> <td>An RF-signal is expected as input, e.g. the bunch clock signal. If ‘Direction’ equals “Output” Signal is equal to “Reference”, modified by ‘Modifier’ (see later) and formed by ‘DigitalParameters’.</td> </tr> </table>	“None”	The signal does not follow a reference (e.g. a detector would be of ‘Direction’ “Input” and doesn’t require a ‘Reference’).	“RF_Signal”	An RF-signal is expected as input, e.g. the bunch clock signal. If ‘Direction’ equals “Output” Signal is equal to “Reference”, modified by ‘Modifier’ (see later) and formed by ‘DigitalParameters’.				
“None”	The signal does not follow a reference (e.g. a detector would be of ‘Direction’ “Input” and doesn’t require a ‘Reference’).								
“RF_Signal”	An RF-signal is expected as input, e.g. the bunch clock signal. If ‘Direction’ equals “Output” Signal is equal to “Reference”, modified by ‘Modifier’ (see later) and formed by ‘DigitalParameters’.								

“External_Clock”	An external clock signal is expected as input, e.g. from a frequency generator. If ‘Direction’ equals “Output” Signal is equal to “Reference”, modified by ‘Modifier’ and formed by ‘DigitalParameters’.				
“Internal_Clock”	The device produces an internal clock signal. If ‘Direction’ equals “Output” Signal is equal to “Reference”, modified by ‘Modifier’ and formed by ‘DigitalParameters’.				
“Event”	Signal waits for clock events over a digital bus. If ‘Direction’ equals “Output” Signal is equal to “Reference”, modified by ‘Modifier’ and formed by ‘DigitalParameters’.				
“Signal”	The reference is formed by the output of another Signal (e.g. named “OtherSignal”). If ‘Direction’ equals “Output” Signal is equal to “Reference”, modified by ‘Modifier’ and formed by ‘DigitalParameters’. An example would be, that a Signal “ClockSignal” creates TTL-Triggers from the an “Internal_clock”. The Signal “DelaySignal” expects “ClockSignal” as reference and delays the reference to form an output.				
“Analog”	Signal waits for an analog reference to be within a certain limit. Then an action is created. If Type is “Trigger” Signal produces a new trigger, if Type is “Gate” Signal swaps the level, modified by ‘Modifier’ and formed by ‘DigitalParameters’. If Type is “Analog” Signal is modified by ‘Modifier’ and formed by ‘AnalogParameters’				
‘Inhibit’	of Type case sensitive string. Can only be one of the following KeyWords : “None” or “Signal”. ‘Reference’ contains Descriptors (see below). The KeyWords mean the following: <table border="0" style="margin-left: 40px;"> <tr> <td style="padding-right: 20px;">“None”</td> <td>No effect</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding-right: 20px;">“Signal”</td> <td>Another Signal acts as input to inhibit this Signal. This Signal must deliver a TTL signal</td> </tr> </table>	“None”	No effect	“Signal”	Another Signal acts as input to inhibit this Signal . This Signal must deliver a TTL signal
“None”	No effect				
“Signal”	Another Signal acts as input to inhibit this Signal . This Signal must deliver a TTL signal				
‘DigitalParameters’	Only to be defined if ‘Type’ equals “Trigger” or “Gate”. ‘DigitalParameters’ contains Descriptors (see below)				

- 'AnalogParameters' Only to be defined if 'Type' equals "Analog". 'AnalogParameters' contains **Descriptors** (see below)
- 'ReferenceParameters' A **Descriptor** which handles descriptions of the reference. Contains **Descriptors** (see below)
- 'InhibitParameters' Only to be defined if 'Inhibit' equals "Signal". 'InhibitParameters' contains **Descriptors** (see below)
- 'ModifierParameters' A **Descriptor** which handles modifications on the signal. 'Modifier' contains **Descriptors** (see below)

In the following, all **Descriptors** which are contained inside the parent **Descriptors** ('DigitalParameters', 'AnalogParameters', 'ReferenceParameters', 'InhibitParameters', 'ModifierParameters') are described:

'DigitalParameters' is only to be defined if 'Type' equals "Trigger" or "Gate". Contains the following **Descriptors**:

- 'Signaling' of **Type** case sensitive string. Can only be one of the following **KeyWords**: "TTL", "LVTTTL", "CMOS", "50Ohm", "OpenCollector", "OpenEmitter", "Voltage"
- 'Polarity' Only to be defined if 'Signaling' does not equal "Voltage". Is of **Type** case sensitive string. Can only be one of the following **KeyWords**: "ActiveHigh" or "ActiveLow". In case of 'Type' = "Trigger" the **Keyword** "ActiveHigh" means trigger on rising edge and "ActiveLow" means trigger on falling edge. In case of 'Type' = 'Gate' the meaning is clear.
- 'ActiveTime' of **Type Integer** measured in pico seconds. The value specifies how long a signal needs to be active to be valid.
- 'DeadTime' of **Type Integer** measured in pico seconds. The value is the time between two signals making both signal valid.
- 'RiseTime' of **Type Integer** measured in pico seconds. The value specifies how long it takes for a valid signal to rise from low to high.
- 'FallTime' of **Type Integer** measured in pico seconds. The value specifies how long it takes for a valid signal to fall from high to low.

- 'MaxJitter' of **Type Integer** measured in pico seconds. The value specifies the maximum time.
- 'HighVoltage' Only to be defined if 'Signaling' equals "Voltage". Is of **Type Float**. It determines the voltage which corresponds to the high-state
- 'LowVoltage' Only to be defined if 'Signaling' equals "Voltage". Is of **Type Float**. It determines the voltage which corresponds to the low-state

'AnalogParameters' is only to be defined if 'Type' equals "Analog". It contains the following **Descriptors**:

- 'MaxVoltage' of **Type Float** measured in Volts. Specifies the maximum voltage allowed.
- 'BitDepth' of **Type Integer**. Specifies the with how many bits the voltage is sampled.

'ReferencesParameters' contains the following **Descriptors**. If 'Reference' equals "None" none of the **Descriptors** are to be defined.

- 'REventNumber' Only to be defined if 'Reference' equals "Event", of **Type Integer** and expects the event number.
- 'RSignalName' Only to be defined if 'Reference' equals "Signal". This means that the Reference is defined by another **Signal**. Is of **Type** case sensitive string and expects the 'Name' of another **Signal**.
- 'RAnalogMin' Only to be defined if 'Reference' equals "Analog", of **Type Float** and expects a Voltage the event number. **Signal** waits for an analog reference to be within a certain limit. The **Value** of 'RAnalogMin' is the minimum **Value** of this limit. If the analog reference is between 'RAnalogMin' and 'RAnalogMax'.
- 'RAnalogMax' Only to be defined if 'Reference' equals "Analog", of **Type Float** and expects a Voltage the event number. **Signal** waits for an analog reference to be within a certain limit. The **Value** of 'RAnalogMax' is the maximum **Value** of this limit. If the analog reference is between 'RAnalogMin' and 'RAnalogMax'.

'InhibitParameters' contains the following **Descriptors**. If 'Inhibit' equals "None", no **Descriptors** are defined:

- 'SignalName' Only to be defined if 'Inhibit' equals "Signal". This means that the 'Inhibit' input is defined by another **Signal** which must be TTL-compatible. Is of **Type** case sensitive string and expects the 'Name' of another **Signal**.
- 'IPolarity' Only to be defined if 'Inhibit' equals "Signal". Is of **Type** case sensitive string. Can only be one of the following **Keywords**: "ActiveHigh" or "ActiveLow". **Signal** is inhibited, as long as 'Inhibit' is active.

'ModifierParameters' contains the following **Descriptors**:

- 'Divider' Only to be defined if 'Modifier' equals "Trigger" or "Gate". Is of **Type Integer**. The frequency of switching from active to inactive is deaccelerated by this amount.
- 'Holdoff' Only to be defined if 'Modifier' equals "Trigger". Of **Type Integer** measured in pico seconds. The **Value** specifies the length of time after a trigger before the next trigger can occur.
- "Delay" The actual **Values** in "Output"- 'Direction' are delayed by this value in pico seconds
- 'ADivider' Only to be defined if 'Modifier' equals "Analog". Is of **Type** positive number **Float**. The **Value** of the analog **Signal** is multiplied by this factor. The resulting Value cannot be larger than 'MaxVoltage' of 'AnalogParameters'.

Examples

- 1) An X-ray detector with external trigger, no inhibit, no divider, no holdoff and no delay

Signal:

```
Name:          Detector
Description:   Pilatus 300k, gets input from Bunch Clock
Direction:    Input
FormFactor:   BNC
Type:         Trigger
Reference:    None
Inhibit:      None
DigitalParameters: # just describing the input parameters
  Signaling:   TTL
  Polarity:    ActiveHigh
  ActiveTime:  100000 [ps]
  DeadTime:    1000 [ps]
  RiseTime:    1000 [ps]
  FallTime:    1000 [ps]
  MaxJitter:   1000 [ps]
ModifierParameters:
  Divider:     1
  Holdoff:     0
  Delay:       0
```

- 2) A signal which is generated by using the accelerator RF-signal, with delay 59 ns and divider of 10

Signal:

```
Name:          Bunch Clock
Description:   Bunch Clock Signal as Reference for some Instruments, e.g. Detector
Direction:    Output
FormFactor:   LEMO_00
Type:         Gate
Reference:    Signal
Inhibit:      None
DigitalParameters: #Required fields if 'Trigger' or 'Gate' are selected as Type
  Signaling:   TTL
  Polarity:    ActiveHigh
  ActiveTime:  100000 [ps]
  DeadTime:    1000 [ps]
  RiseTime:    1000 [ps]
  FallTime:    1000 [ps]
  MaxJitter:   1000 [ps]
ReferenceParameters:
  RSignalName: RF-Signal # generated from some other Signal, not listed here
ModifierParameters:
  Divider:     10
  Holdoff:     0
  Delay:       59000
```


3) A detector triggered by reference and inhibited by signal created by an event, but delayed by 10ns

Signal1:

Name: Inhibit for Detector
Description: Signal to inhibit Detector acquisition
Direction: Output
FormFactor LEMO_00
Type: Trigger
Reference: Event
Inhibit: None
DigitalParameters:
 Signaling: LVTTTL
 Polarity: ActiveHigh
ReferenceParameters:
 REventNumber: 195

Signal2:

Name: Detector
Description: Pilatus 300k, gets reference from RF-Signal and inhibit from Signal1
Direction: Input
FormFactor: BNC
Type: Trigger
Reference: RF_signal
Inhibit: Signal
DigitalParameters: # just describing the input parameters
 Signaling: TTL
 Polarity: ActiveHigh
 ActiveTime: 100000 [ps]
 DeadTime: 1000 [ps]
 RiseTime: 1000 [ps]
 FallTime: 1000 [ps]
 MaxJitter: 1000 [ps]
InhibitParameters:
 ISignalName: Inhibit for Detector
 IPolarity: ActiveHigh
ModifierParameters:
 Divider: 1
 Holdoff: 0
 Delay: 10000

The JSON scheme

In the following the generic JSON scheme is listed. Further below, the three examples from top are printed.

The generic JSON Scheme

```
{
  "$schema": "http://json-schema.org/draft-07/schema#",
  "type": "object",
  "properties": {
    "Signal": {
      "type": "object",
      "properties": {
        "Name": {
          "type": "string"
        },
        "Description": {
          "type": "string"
        },
        "Direction": {
          "type": "string",
          "enum": [
            "Input",
            "Output"
          ]
        }
      }
    },
    "FormFactor": {
      "type": "string",
      "enum": [
        "BNC",
        "SMA",
        "LEMO_00",
        "FO"
      ]
    },
    "Type": {
      "type": "string",
      "enum": [
        "Trigger",
        "Gate",
        "Analog"
      ]
    },
    "Reference": {
      "type": "string",
      "enum": [
        "None",
        "RF_signal",
        "External_Clk",
        "Internal_Clk",
        "Event",
        "Signal",
        "Analog"
      ]
    }
  }
}
```


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```

},
  "Inhibit": {
    "type": "string",
    "enum": [
      "None",
      "Signal"
    ]
  },
  "DigitalParameters": {
    "type": "object",
    "description": "Required if Type is Trigger or Gate",
    "properties": {
      "Signaling": {
        "type": "string",
        "enum": [
          "TTL",
          "LVTTTL",
          "CMOS",
          "500hm",
          "OpenCollector",
          "OpenEmitter",
          "Voltage"
        ]
      },
      "Polarity": {
        "type": "string",
        "enum": [
          "ActiveHigh",
          "ActiveLow"
        ]
      },
      "ActiveTime": {
        "type": "integer",
        "description": "[ps]"
      },
      "DeadTime": {
        "type": "integer",
        "description": "[ps]"
      },
      "RiseTime": {
        "type": "integer",
        "description": "[ps]"
      },
      "FallTime": {
        "type": "integer",
        "description": "[ps]"
      },
      "MaxJitter": {
        "type": "integer",
        "description": "[ps]"
      },
      "HighVoltage": {
        "type": "number",
        "description": "[V], Required if Signalling is Voltage"
      },
      "LowVoltage": {
        "type": "number",
        "description": "[V], Required if Signalling is Voltage"
      }
    }
  }
}

```



```

    },
    "AnalogParameters": {
      "type": "object",
      "description": "Required if Type is Trigger or Analog",
      "properties": {
        "MaxVoltage": {
          "type": "number",
          "description": "[V]"
        },
        "BitDepth": {
          "type": "integer"
        }
      }
    },
    "ReferenceParameters": {
      "type": "object",
      "properties": {
        "REventNumber": {
          "type": "integer",
          "description": "Required if Reference is Event"
        },
        "RSignalName": {
          "type": "string",
          "description": "Required if Reference is Signal"
        },
        "RAnalogMin": {
          "type": "number",
          "description": "Required if Reference is Analog"
        },
        "RAnalogMax": {
          "type": "number",
          "description": "Required if Reference is Analog"
        }
      }
    },
    "InhibitParameters": {
      "type": "object",
      "properties": {
        "ISignalName": {
          "type": "string",
          "description": "Required if Inhibit is Signal"
        },
        "IPolarity": {
          "type": "string",
          "enum": [
            "ActiveHigh",
            "ActiveLow"
          ],
          "description": "Required if Inhibit is Signal"
        }
      }
    },
    "ModifierParameters": {
      "type": "object",
      "properties": {
        "Divider": {
          "type": "integer",
          "description": "Required if Type is Trigger or Gate"
        },
        "Holdoff": {

```



```
        "type": "integer",
        "description": "Required if Type is Trigger or Gate"
    },
    "ADivider": {
        "type": "number",
        "description": "Required if Type is Analog"
    }
}
},
"required": [
    "Name",
    "Description",
    "Direction",
    "FormFactor",
    "Type",
    "Reference",
    "Inhibit"
]
}
}
```


The JSON scheme for the examples mentioned above.

In the following the JSON schemes match the examples from above:

- 1) An X-ray detector with external trigger, no inhibit, no divider, no holdoff and no delay

*** JSON of Example 1

```
{
  "Signal": {
    "Name": "Detector",
    "Description": "Pilatus 300k, gets input from Bunch Clock",
    "Direction": "Input",
    "FormFactor": "BNC",
    "Type": "Trigger",
    "Reference": "None",
    "Inhibit": "None",
    "DigitalParameters": {
      "Signaling": "TTL",
      "Polarity": "ActiveHigh",
      "ActiveTime": 100000,
      "DeadTime": 1000,
      "RiseTime": 1000,
      "FallTime": 1000,
      "MaxJitter": 1000
    },
    "ModifierParameters": {
      "Divider": 1
      "Holdoff": 0
      "Delay": 0
    }
  }
}
```


2) A signal which is generated by using the accelerator RF-signal, with delay 59 ns and divider of 10

*** JSON of Example 2

```
{
  "Signal1": {
    "Name": "Bunch Clock",
    "Description": "Bunch Clock Signal as Reference for some Instruments, e.g. Detector ",
    "Direction": "Output",
    "FormFactor": "LEMO_00",
    "Type": "Gate",
    "Reference": "Signal",
    "Inhibit": "None",
    "DigitalParameters": {
      "Signaling": "TTL",
      "Polarity": "ActiveHigh",
      "ActiveTime": 100000,
      "DeadTime": 1000,
      "RiseTime": 1000,
      "FallTime": 1000,
      "MaxJitter": 1000
    },
    "ReferenceParameters": {
      "RSignalName": "RF-Signal"
    },
    "ModifierParameters": {
      "Divider": 10,
      "Holdoff": 0,
      "Delay": 59000
    }
  }
}
```


3) A detector triggered by reference and inhibited by signal created by an event delayed by 10ns

*** JSON of Example 3

```
{
  "Signal1": {
    "Name": " Inhibit for Detector ",
    "Description": "Input signal to inhibit Detector acquisition",
    "Direction": "Output",
    "FormFactor": "LEMO_00",
    "Type": "Trigger",
    "Reference": "Event",
    "Inhibit": "None",
    "DigitalParameters": {
      "Signaling": "LVTTTL",
      "Polarity": "ActiveHigh"
    },
    "ReferenceParameters": {
      "REventNumber": 195
    }
  },
  "Signal2": {
    "Name": "Detector",
    "Description": " Pilatus 300k, gets reference from RF-Signal and inhibit from Signal1",
    "Direction": "Input",
    "FormFactor": "BNC",
    "Type": "Trigger",
    "Reference": "RF_signal",
    "Inhibit": "Signal",
    "DigitalParameters": {
      "Signaling": "TTL",
      "Polarity": "ActiveHigh",
      "ActiveTime": 100000,
      "DeadTime": 1000,
      "RiseTime": 1000,
      "FallTime": 1000,
      "MaxJitter": 1000
    },
    "InhibitParameters": {
      "ISignalName": "Inhibit for Detector",
      "IPolarity": "ActiveHigh"
    },
    "ModifierParameters": {
      "Divider": 1,
      "Holdoff": 0,
      "Delay": 10000
    }
  }
}
```

